

Research sample of the research on digital divide in education in the period 2015-2024.

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#	1 st Author	Title	Year	Cit	FWCI
1	Ajonbadi, H.A.	The Anathema of Digital Divide in the Nigerian Higher Education: Lessons from the Pandemic. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-40194-7_10	2023	3	4,92
2	AlSadrani, B.	The digital divide in inclusive classrooms. https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.19.3.5	2020	13	1,04
3	AlShawabkeh, A.	Technology-based Learning and the Digital Divide for Deaf/Hearing Students During Covid-19: Academic Justice Lens in Higher Education. https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/85175839177	2023	1	0,26
4	Amirova, A.	The impact of the digital divide on synchronous online teaching in Kazakhstan during COVID-19 school closures. https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2022.1083651	2023	7	1,98
5	Arslan, S.	Digital Divide vs. Inclusive Thinking: The Educational Television in Turkey. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-99622-2_7	2022	1	1,01
6	Aziz, A.	Digital Access, Resources, and Literacy: Mapping the Digital Divide and ICT Learning Challenges among Undergraduate Students in Bangladesh. https://doi.org/10.1163/22142312-bja10064	2024	0	
7	Barra, C.	Digital divide, gender gap, and entrepreneurial orientation: How to foster technology adoption among Pakistani higher education students? https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seps.2024.101904	2024	8	5,07
8	Cheshmehzangi, A.	The growing digital divide in education among primary and secondary children during the COVID-19 pandemic: An overview of social exclusion and education equality issues. https://doi.org/10.1080/10911359.2022.2062515	2023	28	11,54
9	Deng, X.	Digital Inequality and Two Levels of the Digital Divide in Online Learning: A Mixed Methods Study of Underserved College Students. https://doi.org/10.62273/SSIF6302	2024	1	
10	Di Pietro, G.	Changes in Italy's education-related digital divide. https://doi.org/10.1111/ecaf.12471	2021	12	0,92
11	Dolan, J.E.	Splicing the divide: A review of research on the evolving digital divide among K-12 students. https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2015.1103147	2016	139	3,52
12	Faloye, S.T.	Understanding the impact of the digital divide on South African students in higher educational institutions. https://doi.org/10.1080/20421338.2021.1983118	2022	24	2,14
13	Gandolfi E	A new educational normal an intersectionality-led exploration of education, learning technologies, and diversity during COVID-19. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2021.101637	2021	48	4,2
14	González-Chouciño, M.A.	Analysis of the Third Digital Divide in Relation to Digital Socialization Itineraries among University Students in Uruguay. https://doi.org/10.3390/soc13120252	2023	2	0,77

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15	Gremigni, E.	Overcoming new forms of digital divide: Some remarks on the need for media education. https://doi.org/10.13136/isr.v8i1.221	2018	5	0,63
16	Gu, J.	Family conditions and the accessibility of online education: The digital divide and mediating factors. https://doi.org/10.3390/su13158590	2021	25	1,6
17	Hatlevik, O.E.	Exploring educators' perceived possibilities and obstacles related to access and use of ICT: Revealing the digital divide in Norwegian Adult Education centres. https://doi.org/10.18261/njdl.18.1.2	2023	2	0,42
18	Hohlfeld, T. N.	An examination of seven years of technology integration in Florida schools: Through the lens of the Levels of Digital Divide in Schools. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2017.05.017	2017	62	3,16
19	Karabacak, K.	Examination of level of teacher candidates' using smart phone technology and benefiting from the opportunities it presents in the context of digital divide. https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/84957572383	2015	1	0,23
20	Kumi-Yeboah, A.	Strategies for overcoming the digital divide during the COVID-19 pandemic in higher education institutions in Ghana. https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13356	2023	14	3,95
21	Martin, F	From digital divide to digital equity: Systematic review of two decades of research on educational digital divide factors, dimensions, and interventions. https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2024.2425442	2024	0	
22	McFarlane, D.	Closing the digital divide in education: an innovative review of demand and supply side policies in four ASEAN member states. http://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v13i6.28011	2024	0	
23	Mendels, J.	Falling between the cracks: Bedouin students and the digital divide during the Covid-19 crisis. https://doi.org/10.30547/WORLDOFMEDIA.2.2024.7	2024	0	
24	Mendoza-Lozano, F.A.	The digital divide between high school students in Colombia. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.telpol.2021.102226	2021	7	0,4
25	Prajaknate, P.	Information Communication Technologies (ICT) for education projects in ASEAN: Can we close the digital divide? https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-2815-1_6	2017	6	0,46
26	Quaicoe, J.S.	Teachers' digital literacy and digital activity as digital divide components among basic schools in Ghana. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-020-10158-8	2020	41	2,29
27	Quaicoe, J.S.	Factors determining digital divide in Ghana's basic schools. https://doi.org/10.1109/ISTAFRICA.2015.7190518	2015	7	1,98
28	Quaicoe, J.S.	Digital divide in learning services in Ghana's basic school. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-47440-3_9	2016	1	
29	Radovanović, D.	Overcoming digital divides in higher education: Digital literacy beyond Facebook. https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444815588323	2015	63	2,21
30	Russo, K.	The digital divide and higher education. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-30808-6_6	2023	1	1,68
31	Schroot, T.	Digital competences in the educational sphere: A case study from Italy. https://doi.org/10.1515/9783839468890-012	2024	0	

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32	Sezgin, S.	Exploring the Digital Divide in Open Education: A Comparative Analysis of Undergraduate Students. https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v25i1.7236	2024	2	1,65
33	Soomro, K. A.	Development of an instrument to measure Faculty's information and communication technology access (FICTA). https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-017-9599-9	2018	33	1,62
34	Soomro, K.A.	Digital divide among higher education faculty. https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-020-00191-5	2020	121	6,07
35	Spiteri, C.	Bridging the digital divide for e-learning students through adaptive VLEs. https://doi.org/10.1109/TALE.2016.7851796	2017	4	0,3
36	Subramaniam, L.	Digital Divide and University Students' Online Learning amidst Covid-19 Pandemic in Malaysia. https://doi.org/10.1515/libri-2023-0115	2024	0	
37	Talandron-Felipe, M.M.P.	The digital divide among students and support initiatives in the time of Covid-19. https://library.apsce.net/index.php/ICCE/article/view/4063	2020	6	0,59
38	Tirado-Morueta, R.	The relativity of sociodemographic determinism on the digital divide in high school students in Ecuador. https://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32953.28004	2017	8	0,52
39	Val, S.	Analysis of Digital Teacher Education: Key Aspects for Bridging the Digital Divide and Improving the Teaching-Learning Process. https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14030321	2024	6	4,2
40	Ventrella, F.M.	Examining digital capital and digital inequalities in Canadian elementary Schools: Insights from teachers. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2023.102070	2024	9	7,7
41	Wang	A "live" and E-education in a frontier area in China under the perspective of the philosophy of technology. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12118-4	2024	0	
42	Wang, L.	Lost in mobile? Exploring the mobile internet digital divide among Chinese college students. https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-021-00267-w	2021	12	0,93
43	Wild, S.	How do the digital competences of students in vocational schools differ from those of students in cooperative higher education institutions in Germany? https://doi.org/10.1186/s40461-020-00091-y	2020	34	3,27
44	Yaqin, L.N.	Addressing the Digital Divide in Indonesian Higher Education: Insights, Implications, and Potential Solutions. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-7645-4_13	2023	3	2,26
45	Yersel, B.	Digital divide and emergency remote education: reconsidering the use of educational radio during the pandemic. https://doi.org/10.17718/tojde.1101847	2023	4	1,11
46	Zhang, C.	College students' literacy, ChatGPT activities, educational outcomes, and trust from a digital divide perspective. https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448241301741	2024	1	
47	Zheng et al	Dynamic Teacher's Technology Adoption During the COVID-19 Pandemic. https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241237858	2024	0	
48	Zhong, B.	Is There a Digital Divide Between Urban Students and Migrant Students in China? https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211016387	2021	10	1,84